

Apparent Molar Volume and Acoustic Behaviour of Zirconyl Soap Solutions in Benzene-Chloroform Mixture

K. N. MEHROTRA* and M. ANIS

Department of Chemistry, Institute of Basic Sciences, Dr. B. R. Ambedkar University, Khandari Road, Agra-282 002

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The ultrasonic velocity measurements have been used to obtain information regarding various acoustic parameters and solute-solvent interactions in pure liquids, liquid mixtures and electrolytic solutions¹.

The present work deals with the determination of apparent molar volume and ultrasonic velocity of zirconyl soaps in benzene-chloroform mixture (4 : 1, v/v). The results were used to study the CMC, soap-soap and soap-solvent interactions and various acoustic parameters.

Calculations :

The adiabatic compressibility (β), apparent molar volume (ϕ_v)², apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_k) and solvation number (S_n)³ were calculated using the relationship,

$$\beta = v^{-2} \rho^{-1} \quad (1)$$

$$\phi_v = \frac{1000}{c \rho_o} (\rho_o - \rho) + \frac{M}{\rho_o} \quad (2)$$

$$\phi_k = \frac{1000}{c \rho_o} (\rho_o \beta - \rho \beta_o) + \frac{M \beta_o}{\rho_o} \quad (3)$$

$$S_n = \frac{n_o}{n} \left(1 - \frac{\bar{V} \beta}{n_o \bar{V}_o \beta_o} \right) \quad (4)$$

where, v_o , v ; ρ_o , ρ ; β_o , β and \bar{V}_o , \bar{V} are ultrasonic velocity, density, adiabatic compressibility and molar volume of solvent and solution, respectively; n_o , n and M_o , M are number of mole and molecular weight of solvent and soap respectively.

Results and Discussion

Apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) : The density (ρ) of soap solutions increases with increasing concentration and chainlength of soap (Table 1). The results obey Root's equation,

$$\rho = \rho_o + Ac - Bc^{3/2} \quad (5)$$

The magnitudes of constants A (40.5, 62.5, 81.0 and 103.5) and B (68.5, 136.9, 143.9 and 164.4) depend upon the chainlength of soap. The plots of ρ vs c show break at a definite soap concentration which corresponds to the CMC. The values of the CMC are in agreement with those obtained from ultrasonic velocity, viscosity and conductivity measurements (Table 2).

The apparent molar volume (ϕ_v) at first increases and then decreases with the increase in soap concentration. The values of ϕ_v were found to be positive and increase with increasing chainlength of soap (Table 1). The limiting apparent molar volume or partial molar volume of soap (ϕ_v^o) was estimated by Masson equation⁴,

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^o + S_v c^{1/2} \quad (6)$$

where, ϕ_v^o is a measure of soap-solvent interaction and S_v represents the variation of ϕ_v with c .

The increase in the values of ϕ_v^o (298, 336, 374 and 412 $\times 10^{-6}$ m³ mol⁻¹) with increasing chainlength of soap may be attributed to the change in intrinsic volume and the positive values of S_v (90, 110, 130 and 140 $\times 10^{-6}$) confirm

TABLE I—DENSITY (ρ), APPARENT MOLAR VOLUME (ϕ_v) AND APPARENT MOLAR COMPRESSIBILITY (ϕ_k) OF ZIRCONYL SOAPS IN BENZENE-CHLOROFORM MIXTURE (4 : 1, v/v) AT 40 \pm 0.05 $^\circ$

c mol dm ⁻³	ρ (kg m ⁻³)				$10^6 \phi_v$ (m ³ mol ⁻¹)				$-10^7 \phi_k$ (m ⁵ N ⁻¹ kg ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)			
	Hexa- noate	Octa- noate	Deca- noate	Doode- canoate	Hexa- noate	Octa- noate	Deca- noate	Dode- canoate	Hexa- noate	Octa- noate	Deca- noate	Dode- canoate
0.01	989.1	989.3	989.5	989.7	310.98	347.13	383.52	419.92	1.991	2.785	3.579	4.473
0.02	989.4	989.7	990.0	990.4	310.98	352.16	393.63	430.04	1.591	2.237	2.782	3.676
0.03	989.6	990.0	990.5	991.0	314.35	357.22	396.10	436.78	1.425	1.938	2.583	3.278
0.04	989.8	990.3	990.9	991.6	316.04	359.75	401.21	440.15	1.393	1.864	2.429	3.154
0.05	990.0	991.0	992.3	993.8	317.05	353.18	383.52	409.81	1.272	2.187	3.079	4.290
0.06	991.1	992.6	994.0	995.8	302.56	333.62	366.66	392.95	1.772	2.765	3.691	4.882
0.07	992.3	994.0	996.0	998.2	290.76	322.55	350.29	375.14	2.299	3.278	4.312	5.374
0.08	993.3	995.4	997.7	1000.4	284.44	314.24	341.73	364.30	2.558	3.476	4.580	5.745
0.09	994.5	997.0	999.6	1002.5	277.27	305.53	332.95	356.09	2.815	3.806	4.798	5.922
0.10	995.5	998.5	1001.5	1005.9	273.56	299.58	325.87	348.12	2.970	3.941	5.032	6.252

Uncertainties : ρ : ± 0.1 kg m⁻³; ϕ_v : $\pm (0.01-0.10) \times 10^{-6}$ m³ mol⁻¹; ϕ_k : $\pm 1 \times 10^{-10}$ m⁵ N⁻¹ kg⁻¹ mol⁻¹.

NOTE

TABLE 2—CMC, EXTRAPOLATED AND EXPERIMENTAL VALUES OF ULTRASONIC VELOCITY (v_0) AND ADIABATIC COMPRESSIBILITY (β_0) IN BENZENE-CHLOROFORM MIXTURES (4 : 1, v/v) AT $40 \pm 0.05^\circ$

Soap	CMC (mol dm ⁻³)					v_0 m s ⁻¹	$10^{10}\beta_0$ m ² N ⁻¹
	v vs c	ϕ_v vs $c^{1/2}$	ρ vs c	η vs c	k vs c		
Hexanoate	0.050	0.050	0.050	0.051	0.052	1 027.00	9 587 5
Octanoate	0.046	0.046	0.047	0.048	0.048	1 027.10	9.583 8
Decanoate	0.042	0.043	0.043	0.042	0.042	1 027.15	9.582 5
Dodecanoate	0.039	0.040	0.039	0.039	0.038	1 027.20	9.580 0
Experimental						1 026.60	9.595 0

TABLE 3—ULTRASONIC VELOCITY (v), ADIABATIC COMPRESSIBILITY (β) AND SOLVATION NUMBER (S_n) OF ZIRCONYL SOAPS IN A BENZENE-CHLOROFORM MIXTURE (4 : 1, v/v) AT $40 \pm 0.05^\circ$

c mol dm ⁻³	v (m s ⁻¹)				$10^{10}\beta$ (m ² N ⁻¹)				S_n (C.G.S unit)			
	Hexa- noate	Octa- noate	Deca- noate	Dode- canoate	Hexa- noate	Octa- noate	Deca- noate	Dode- canoate	Hexa- noate	Octa- noate	Deca- noate	Dode- canoate
0.01	1 027.4	1 027.6	1 027.8	1 028.1	9.578	9.572	9.566	9.559	2.01	2.72	3.43	4.22
0.02	1 027.7	1 028 1	1 028.4	1 028.9	9.569	9.559	9.551	9.537	1.54	2.13	2.60	3.43
0.03	1 028.1	1 028 6	1 029.0	1 029.6	9.560	9.547	9.534	9.518	1.38	1 89	2.41	3.04
0.04	1 028.6	1 029.1	1 029.7	1 030.5	9.549	9.535	9.518	9.496	1 36	1.78	2.28	2.93
0.05	1 028.8	1 030.2	1 031.3	1 033.5	9.543	9.507	9.475	9 429	1.23	2.08	2 84	3.93
0.06	1 030.0	1 031.6	1 033.2	1 035.2	9.511	9.466	9.424	9.370	1.66	2 54	3.37	4.44
0.07	1 031.7	1 033.2	1 035.5	1 037.3	9.468	9.416	9.363	9 310	2.15	3.03	3 92	4.82
0.08	1 033.0	1 034 8	1 037.3	1 039.6	9 434	9.381	9.315	9 248	2 38	3.17	4 14	5.13
0.09	1 034.4	1 036.7	1 038.9	1 041.5	9.397	9.332	9.268	9.195	2.60	3.46	4 30	5.26
0.10	1 035.8	1 038.0	1 040.9	1 044.2	9.363	9.295	9.215	9.126	2.75	3.55	4.50	5.55

Uncertainties : $v : \pm 0.1$ m s⁻¹; $\beta : \pm 0.1 \times 10^{-12}$ m² N⁻¹.

strong ion-ion interactions. The difference in the values of ϕ_v^0 for hexanoate and octanoate, octanoate and decanoate, and decanoate and dodecanoate (38.0×10^{-6} m³ mol⁻¹) shows that the contribution of each CH₂ group to partial molar volume is about 9.5×10^{-6} m³ mol⁻¹. Similar results for ϕ_v^0 were also obtained for zirconyl soaps in xylene-methanol mixture (4 : 1, v/v). However, the contribution of each CH₂ group to molar volume for aqueous solutions of sodium formate, acetate, propionate, butyrate and valerate was reported to be 15×10^{-6} m³ mol⁻¹ at 25^os. The difference in the values of CH₂ contribution to ϕ_v^0 may be due to size of anion, nature of cation, composition of solvent mixture and extent of solvation.

Ultrasonic velocity and acoustic parameters : The ultrasonic velocity (v) of soap solutions increases with increasing concentration and chainlength of soap (Table 3). The variation of v with c can be expressed as

$$\frac{dv}{dc} = -\frac{v}{2} \left[\frac{1}{\rho} \left(\frac{d\rho}{dc} \right) + \frac{1}{\beta} \left(\frac{d\beta}{dc} \right) \right] \quad (7)$$

The results (Table 1) show that the density increases while the adiabatic compressibility decreases with increasing soap concentration. Thus, the quantity $d\rho/dc$ is positive while $d\beta/dc$ is negative. Since the values of $\frac{1}{\beta} \left(\frac{d\beta}{dc} \right)$ for soap solutions are larger than that of $\frac{1}{\rho} \left(\frac{d\rho}{dc} \right)$, the concentra-

tion derivative of velocity, dv/dc is positive. The results are in agreement with those of other workers⁶ for electrolytic solutions. The variation of v with c follows the relationship,

$$v = v_0 + Gc \quad (8)$$

where, v_0 is ultrasonic velocity of solvent mixture and G is Garnsey constant⁷. The plots of v vs c are characterised by an intersection of two straight-lines at the CMC and the intercepts of the plots correspond to the ultrasonic velocity of the solvent mixture (v_0) (Table 2). It was found that the value of CMC decreases while of Garnsey's constant increases with increasing chainlength of soap molecule (Table 4).

The decrease in β with increasing c is due to ionisation of soap molecules in dilute solutions. The ions in solutions are surrounded by a layer of solvent molecules firmly bound and oriented towards ions which may be attributed to the influence of electrostatic fields of ions and thus the internal pressure increases which lowers the compressibility of the solutions, i.e. the solutions become harder to compress⁸. The decrease in β at higher soap concentrations may be due to the close packing of ionic head groups in the micelles which results in an increase in ionic repulsion and finally of internal pressure. The adiabatic compressibility (β) of solutions follows Bachem relationship⁹,

$$\beta = \beta_0 + Ac + Bc^{3/2} \quad (9)$$

The values of constants A and B were determined from the

TABLE 4—ACOUSTIC PARAMETERS OF ZIRCONYL SOAPS AT $40 \pm 0.05^\circ$

Soap	G	Bachem's equation		$10^6 \phi_k^0$	$-10^7 \phi_k^0$	$10^6 S_v$	$10^7 S_k$
		$-10^{10} A$	$10^{10} B$				
Hexanoate	33.33	1.74	3.15	298	2.16	90	4.11
Octanoate	50.00	2.45	5.07	336	3.08	110	5.95
Decanoate	63.33	2.92	5.48	374	3.67	130	6.15
Dodecanoate	76.67	3.88	7.26	412	4.90	140	9.04

intercept and slope of the plots of $(\beta - \beta_0)/c$ vs $c^{1/2}$. It was found that the values of constant A decrease while of B increase with increasing chainlength of soap molecules (Table 4).

It follows from Gucker's limiting law¹⁰ using Debye-Hückel theory¹¹ that the apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_k) is related to soap concentration (c) by the relation,

$$\phi_k = \phi_k^0 + S_k c^{1/2} \quad (10)$$

The values of limiting apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_k^0) and constant S_k were obtained from the linear plots of ϕ_k vs $c^{1/2}$ for dilute solutions. The positive values of S_k (Table 4) signify a considerable soap-solvent interaction in dilute solutions¹². The values of ϕ_k^0 are negative and become more negative with an increase in the chainlength of soap molecules (Table 4). The values of ϕ_k become more negative at higher soap concentrations (Table 1) suggesting that the soap-solvent interaction decreases with increasing soap concentration.

The solvation number at first decreases in dilute solutions (upto the CMC) and then increases with increasing soap concentration (Table 3). The solvation number increases with increasing chainlength of soap molecules.

The results confirm that there is a significant interaction between the soap and solvent molecules in dilute solutions. The values of the CMC obtained from different measurements are in agreement and decrease with increasing chainlength of soap molecules.

Experimental

Zirconyl soaps were prepared by direct metathesis of the corresponding potassium soap with aqueous solution of zirconium oxychloride. The soaps were purified by recrystallisation with benzene-methanol mixture and their purity was checked by m.p. (hexanoate, 137° ; octanoate, 146° ; decanoate, 158° ; dodecanoate, 167°), elemental analysis and ir spectra.

The solutions of different concentrations of soaps were prepared in benzene-chloroform mixture (4 : 1, v/v) and were kept for 2 h at $40 \pm 0.05^\circ$ in a thermostat. Density was determined with a dilatometer calibrated with benzene. A multifrequency ultrasonic interferometer (M-83, Mittal Enterprises) was used to measure the ultrasonic velocity at $40 \pm 0.05^\circ$ using a crystal of 1 MHz frequency.

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